

Impact of Black Death in Europe - A Study

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ABSTRACT

A devastating illness known as the plague ravaged Europe from 1347 to 1352. The Black Death was a bacterial infectious disease with a high mortality rate. It claimed the lives of between 25 and 30 million individuals. The outbreak started in Central Asia and moved west over busy trade routes. The plague spread quickly by sea, and then later by land throughout all of Europe. The plague had a significant impact on Europe, leading to increases in per capita income and wages, the abolition of slavery in Western Europe, a reduction in the influence of religious organizations, and the creation of powerful nations. This essay depicts the origins, spread, and Impact of the Black Death in the 3rd and 4th centuries in Europe.

Keywords: Plague, Black Death, Europe, impact, wages.

Introduction

The Pandemic has a long history, but the term itself is yet to be defined by many medical texts. There have been a number of significant pandemics recorded in human history where pandemic related crises have caused enormous negative impacts on health, economies, and even national security globally. In the 1300s, Europe and Asia were both affected by the bubonic plague outbreak known as the Black Death. The arrival of 12 ships from the Black Sea in the port of Messina, Sicily, in 1347 shocked the locals horribly. The sailors were mostly dead, and those that were still living had severe illnesses and black sores that were leaking blood and pus. It was already too late when the Sicilian authorities hurriedly ordered the death ships out of the harbor. Over the following five years, the plague decimated Europe by a third, killing more than 20 million people. Between 1347 and 1351, which spread throughout Europe?

Methodology

The present study on based on the primary and secondary sources and is completely discriptive in nature

Definition of plague

The Plague is another name for this Black Death. The word "plague" comes from the ancient Greek word "plague," which means "stroke" in English. This pack sickness has potent and rapid dissemination.

Symptoms

Patients with the plague experience a high fever, diarrhea, and fainting, and their fingertips and nose develop black blisters. When the body's tiny blood vessels get clogged with bacteria, they started to bleed and became visible under the skin, which caused these black blisters as a plague victim's skin turns black, the disease was also known as the "Black Death."

Types of Black Death

Plague is classified into three types are

Bubonic Plague:

The most prevalent and treatable type of illness is bubonic plague, which is distinguished by enlarged lymph nodes known as “Bubos”. Buboes can be seen in the groin, armpit, or neck and are frequently stiff and excruciatingly painful. Patients risk dying if their condition is not treated.

Pneumonic Plague:

These bacteria invade the lungs. Pneumonic plague victims may experience severe respiratory symptoms. This particular epidemic can quickly develop into multiple organ failure and cause death if left untreated.

Septicemic Plague:

This bacterium enters the bloodstream and quickly spreads to many human tissues and organs, leading to gangrene and organ failure. If a problem is not identified and treated right away, serious consequences may develop.

Characteristics of the black plague

The bubonic plague had a terrible impact on humanity. Its main characteristic was that it cannot live among people. Although the bubonic plague is a rat disease, rodents do not cause it. On the other hand, the plague is a bacilli-type of bacteria. The bacteria that can transfer from one rat to another is known as Yersinia. The microbiologist Alexandre Persin made the initial discovery of it in 1894. Mice were commonly infected by these bacteria. It spreads by fleas from mouse to mouse. The digestive tract of the rat becomes obstructed as a result of this bacteria's colonization and reproduction, and the rat starts to starve. A famished rat begins biting another rat, who eventually bites humans and the dead, spreading the disease to people.

Impact of the Black Death

In 1358 and 1359, the Black Death had a significant impact on politics, the economy, and society. All facets of life, including the social and political system in the devastated areas, were negatively impacted for a very long time. Because so many peasants perished from the plague and there was a labour shortage in the aristocrats' fields, the Black Death had a

significant negative influence on the population living in the 14th century. Some plague victims who survived ended up becoming the next victims. They didn't value virtues, which led to an increase in crimes like sex. As more people lost their partners to disease, the marriage market expanded.

The political impact of the Black Death

Political life was greatly impacted by the Black Death. Peasants had to obtain their lord's permission to leave their communities in the fourteenth century, but following the epidemic, many disregarded the rule and moved from village to village. Farmers started to demand higher salaries as a result of the Black Death, but the rulers refused to increase wages.

The Labor Ordinance, which later became the Labor Act of 1351, was published in 1349, little than a year after the plague. To control them, the government put in place severe regulations. Peasants who disobeyed this legislation were subjected to cruel punishments; as a result, they began several uprisings and battled for their rights. These battles were fierceful. Peasants gathered and marched towards London in 1381. Before the epidemic, women in particular were granted some new property rights that were tailored to the local environment. Until they got remarried, widows in some areas of England were permitted to keep their husband's property.

Social Impact of the Black Death

The 14th-century population were greatly affected by the Black Death. The afflicted areas had much fewer inhabitants. Before the epidemic, there was a system of feudalism in place. Inequality existed between the rich nobles and the poor peasants, and after the epidemic, the more populous peasants died from it, leaving the nobles without workers for their farms. Those that were untouched by the disease had long lives. Many crimes were committed because Plague believed they would be his next victims.

Sexual crimes increased. People losing their partners led to a rise in the marriage market. Some doctors lacked the medical expertise necessary to identify the illness and discover a treatment. To make pilgrimages and gather to worship artifacts, people in the

middle ages traveled to great distances, which facilitated the transmission of bacteria. People who had this illness were removed from their families. The streets were filled with sick kids.

After population declined, competition for land and resources diminished since no one wanted to take care of the sick or bury the dead. The government assigned certain bodies and nurses to assist with the burial of the deceased. Some unaffected farmers moved to the metropolis, while doctors, preachers, and politicians largely fled the cities. As a result of the labour shortage in the villages, wages started to climb. Landlords began offering part of their property for sale to farmers. The aristocracy was overthrown by a pandemic. As inequality continued to decline, the underprivileged also slowly began to rise in society. Slavery was then abolished in Europe. Workers began to struggle for their rights. Several revolts and riots broke out in France in 1358. The medical field has been enhanced even more.

While this was going on, some Europeans were denied employment with the government and kept out of the cities because they thought Jews were to blame for the plague. A few of them were killed. Depression set in among the era's authors and painters. Some of those artists used music and art to convey their anguish and the horror of the Black Death. The Church ruled Europe with total authority before the Black Death, but during the pandemic, corruption was rife and people refused to follow the law. 60% of the clergy left their jobs as the Church lost its influence, and there was a large recruitment effort to fill these positions. Lowering requirements for them Illiterate individuals ran monasteries. The Awakening replaced vernaculars. Survivors protested against physicians who failed to treat the sick, and as a result, the Black Death led to several discoveries in a large portion of Europe.

Economic impact of the Black Death

All economic activity came to a halt as a result of the Black Death, and trade suffered as people were scared to relocate from one location to another. As Plague population dwindled, it became more difficult to plow the fields, harvest crops, and create other things, and farmers began to demand greater salaries. In Europe, English legislation aimed to compel laborers to accept the same salaries as in 1348. In 1360, the sanctions were severe, and laborers who requested excessive wages were imprisoned. On the forehead, fugitives were branded. After the epidemic, many laborers were needed to raise and harvest grain, so some nobility began raising sheep instead. Customers buying meat and woolen items increased

their income. Trade Price increased for imported commodities from other parts of the world occurred as raw material interchange grew challenging and dangerous. Lack of labour caused livestock to die, unharvested crops, and food shortages in the city as a result of starvation in the villages. As food prices increased, the impoverished suffered.

Conclusion

European medieval society was significantly impacted by the Black Death, which also altered the population makeup. Due to this illness, it was permitted for abandoned fields to be utilized for cultivation. The landowners were no longer in control of the serfs. The change from medieval to modern medicine. Even though the Black Death inflicted terrible suffering, it also gave rise to fresh chances for social, cultural, and economic advancement.

End notes

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